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**Experimental study of enclosure
airtightness of an outdoor chamber
using the pulse technique and
blower door method under various
leakage and wind conditions**

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Introduction

Principle

Equipment and setup

Test results

Conclusions

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**1. Real houses
natural environment
36th AIVC**

**2. House-sized chamber
sheltered environment
38th AIVC**

**3. Small chamber
natural environment
39th AIVC**

**4. Impact of steady
wind on the pulse
test
39th AIVC**

**5. Pulse → Infiltration
(one dwelling)
39th AIVC**

**6. Pulse vs. BD in an
extended range
39th AIVC**

**7. Pulse → Infiltration
(multiple dwellings)
Hopefully 40th AIVC**

**8. Further systematic
study of wind impact
Hopefully 40th AIVC**

Sheltered environment comparison
(Oct-2015)

Natural environment comparison
(Feb-2017)

Impact of steady wind (Oct-2017)

The pulse technique is implemented by releasing a measured amount of compressed air from an air tank over short period of time (1.5 s) to the test space and monitor the pressure response in the space.

Tank unit

Compressor motor

Pressure transducer

Air tank (10 bar)

Solenoid valve

Control unit

Enter tester info and building info

PULSE 100% t1 9.9 Bar t2 0.0 Bar 14:38:28 20/03/2018 91

Number of Steps in Test	2 Steps >
Tester ID	AM
Tank 1 Volume(L)	60
Tank 2 Volume (L)	0

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2.84m × 2.23m × 2.03m

PULSE-80

DBB

PULSE-60

NC tests

SW tests

Openings sealed in various scenarios for the NC tests

Scenario	1	2	3	4	5	6
Descriptor	Compliance test: All openings were sealed except background vents	Air brick unsealed	Radiator vent and static vent unsealed	Trickle vents, sink traps, boiler vent, dryer vent and passive stack vent unsealed	Bathroom vent, cooker extract and shower vent unsealed	All openings were sealed except background vents and boiler vent

Trend of P4 in the six scenarios given by DBB in pressurisation mode and PULSE-80

Setup of blower door (fan off only)

Setup of Pulse unit

Petrol driven multiple gear portable fan

Wind direction 1 (used in scenario 1,2 and 3)

Wind direction 2 (Only used in scenario 3)

Scenario	1	2	3a	3b
Vent conditions	Shower extract vent was sealed	Shower extract, tumble drier vent, cooker hood vent, and static vent were sealed	Shower extract, radiator vent, cat flap, cooker hood vent, and static vent were sealed	
Wind direction	1	1	1	2
Baseline	Fan off	Fan off	Fan off	Fan off
Wind 1 (m/s)	2.5-3.5, up to 4	2.5-3.5, up to 4	2.5-3.5, up to 4	2.5-3.5, up to 4
Wind 2 (m/s)	4-5, up to 7	4-5, up to 7	n/a	n/a
Wind 3 (m/s)	6.5-7.5, up to 8.7	6.5-7.5, up to 8.7	n/a	n/a
Wind 4 (m/s)	n/a	8.5-9.5, up to 11.7	n/a	n/a

Air permeability at 4 Pa (m³/h·m²) measured by DBB and PULSE-60 for fan off condition

Equipment	DBB	PULSE-60	Mean % difference between DBB and PULSE 60
	P4(m ³ /h·m ²)	P4(m ³ /h·m ²)	
Scenario 1:	9.87	9.89	-1.69%
	10.07	10.03	
	9.75	10.28	
Mean	9.90(±1.75%)	10.07(±2.10%)	
Scenario 2:	8.18	7.68	-1.62%
	7.70	8.09	
	7.85	8.34	
Mean	7.91 (±3.45%)	8.04 (±4.41%)	
Scenario 3:	9.00	9.53	-10.84%
	8.95	9.48	
	7.98	10.05	
Mean	8.64 (±7.68%)	9.69(±3.79%)	

Impact of various wind conditions on the measurement of air permeability at 4 Pa ($\text{m}^3/\text{h}\cdot\text{m}^2$) in 3 different scenarios

Scenario 1

Scenario 2

Test repeatability in different conditions					
Test condition	Baseline	Wind 1	Wind 2	Wind 3	Wind 4
Scenario 1	±3.4%	±2.7%	±15.7%	±7.3%	n/a
Scenario 2	±4.40%	±2.10%	±2.50%	±25.60%	±15.80%
Wind condition compared to baseline					
Scenario 1	n/a	-1.9%	-16.3%	-20.8%	n/a
Scenario 2	n/a	2.11%	-2.73%	-24%	-14.10%

Scenario 3

Test repeatability in different conditions			
Test condition	Baseline	Direction 1	Direction 2
Scenario 3	±4.3%	±15.2%	±16.8%
Wind direction compared to baseline			
Scenario 3	n/a	-10.0%	-10.9%

- In NC tests, the DBB and the pulse methods followed a similar trend, with a slightly larger discrepancy than (Zheng 2017).
- In SW tests, a similar overall deviation range with that obtained in the NC tests was achieved. But both are slightly higher than that obtained in previous sheltered environment study. It is considered that blower door installation, weather condition, pulse model and extrapolation might contribute to the increase in deviation between the two methods in measuring P4.
- When the wind is less than 3.5 m/s, the impact of wind on the pulse test is negligible. When the wind speed was increased to between 4.5 m/s and 9 m/s, the pulse test became less repeatable, and the measured air permeability was decreased by 2.7%-24%. The initial results also suggested the opening distribution might change the way wind impacts the pulse measurement.
- This steady wind study provides insight of how wind affects the pulse measurement based on a small outdoor chamber. These tests represent the observations seen on a limited number of tests for this case study and further experimental investigations are now required in the field of actual dwellings to determine the validity of the findings in this study.

Many thanks!

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